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Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY TO DETERMINE THE RATE
OF SHORTAGE OF VITAMIN D ESPECIALLY IN THE LOW
STANDARD URBAN COMMUNITY****Dr. Muhammad Sadiq, Dr. Muhammad Shehroz Sarwar, Dr. Hafiz u Rehman**
Muhammad Medical College Mir Pur Khas**Abstract:**

Objective: the objective of the study was to determine the rate of shortage of vitamin D especially in the low standard urban community.

Methods: This research study was cross-sectional and organized in those areas of Lahore where standard of living is low. The selection was made randomly and people included were healthy. These participants were enlightened about agreement. For statistical assessment, logistic regression and one-way analysis were used. By means of a kit, estimation for the serum levels of 25-hydroxy vitamin D was done. Kit was taken from Roche Diagnostic.

Results: Total people included in this study were 858. Out of these, the percentage for men and women were 351 (41%) and 507 (59%) respectively. The age bracket for both genders was from 18 – 16 years. The insufficiency (20.0 – 29.9 ng/ml) of vitamin D noticed was 269 (31.4%) whereas, deficiency (< 20 ng/ml) of vitamin D observed was 501 (58.4%). The participants were also checked for smoking and education. After this estimation, the females were found more deficient of vitamin D comparative to males.

Conclusion: The study concluded that in urban community, the shortage of vitamin D is more in females as compared to males which is a serious hazard to people health. Medical staff should resolve this issue by giving people attention.

Keywords: Socio-economic factors, Vitamin D, deficiency / insufficiency, Urban population.

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INTRODUCTION:

Syndrome caused by deficiency of vitamin D (Hypovitaminosis) is a serious issue related to health around the globe [1]. When the serum levels of 25 (OH) D in the range of 20 – 29.9 ng/ml, then it is known as insufficiency of vitamin D. On the other hand, when serum levels of 25 – hydroxy vitamin D {25 (OH)D} are less than 20 ng/ml then, it is called vitamin D deficiency [1, 2]. In Pakistan, the shortage of vitamin D reached to the extent of (70% - 92%). However, in South Asia, prevalence of vitamin D deficiency reached on the top level [3, 4, 5, 6]. Those people who were vagrantly visiting hospital due to several sorts of diseases were included in this study [4, 5]. In Lahore research study was conducted in 10 dissimilar locations. Adults were observed with serum levels of 25 (OH)D. 74% was the percentage of widespread of vitamin D deficiency in these studies [7]. These people were examined for the levels of vitamin D as recommended by physicians. No study was conducted previously to check the extant of vitamin D deficiency in Pakistan's common population. The objective of the present research study was to determine the rate of shortage of vitamin D especially in the low standard urban community.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

Total 926 individuals who were physically fit were chose for this crucible study. These individuals were from eastern Lahore and were living in Sultanabad having a low standard of living. These individuals were examined for the widespread shortage of vitamin B-12, vitamin B-6 and folate [8]. This research study was organized for 53,000 individuals in a population of 4000 houses [9]. Houses and people from this population were chosen irregularly. This was also started in the studies held prior [10]. The time duration for this crucible study was from

September 2016 to October 2017. Ethic Review Committee of Services hospital, Lahore accepted this research study. Total people enrolled for this study were physically fit and 858 in numbers. These participants signed a written agreement. These individuals were not receiving any supplements for vitamin D for last 6 months. Any minor or serious disease was not observed in these people. A questionnaire was arranged. An estimation regarding education, house hold income, smoking and demographic features was made. When the serum levels of 25 (OH)D are in the range of 20 – 29.9 ng/ml, then it is known as insufficiency of vitamin D whereas, when the serum levels of 25-hydroxy vitamin 25(OH)D are less than 20 ng/ml, then it is referred as vitamin D deficiency. By means of commercially available kit, serum levels of 25 (OH)D were assessed. This kit was based on electrochemiluminescence immunoassay (Elecsys Roche Diagnostics, Indianapolis). In a condition of fasting, sample of blood was taken. For the illustration of quantitative values, mean $\pm$ standard deviation was used. The values were compared by means of one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) whereas, multiple comparisons were made by using Tukey's comparison of gender with the odds of having vitamin D deficiency, logistic regression was used. The value of $P < 0.05$ was remarked as limit.

RESULTS:

Total people included in this study were 858. Out of these, percentage for men and women were 351 (49%) and 507 (59%) respectively. The limit of age for both genders was from 18 to 16 years and mean age was 32.5 ± 10.7 years. The mean age of males and females was 32.1 ± 11.5 years and 32.8 ± 10.1 years respectively. No valuable differences were noticed between mean ages of both genders ($P=0.32$).

Table No 01: Mean serum concentrations of vitamin D with respect to demographic characteristics and smoking status

Variable	Quantity (%)	25(OH)D (ng/ml) Mean $\pm$ SD	ANOVA P – value
Gender	Male	351 (40.9)	24.32 $\pm$ 7.76
	Female	507 (59.1)	16.94 $\pm$ 6.91
Ethnicity	Hindku/Hazara/Kashmiri	461 (53.7)	20.11 $\pm$ 8.59
	Pathan/Swati	293 (34.2)	19.74 $\pm$ 7.67
	Gilgiti/Punjabi/Others	104 (12.1)	19.92 $\pm$ 7.20
Education	No education & < Middle	324 (37.8)	18.33 $\pm$ 7.31
	Middle	192 (22.4)	21.12 $\pm$ 9.77
	Matric	201 (23.4)	21.21 $\pm$ 7.71
	Intermediate & above	141 (16.4)	20.31 $\pm$ 7.41
House hold income***	< 5000 PKR	399 (46.5)	20.02 $\pm$ 8.1
	5000 – 10000 PKR	358 (41.7)	19.58 $\pm$ 8.0
	> 10000 PKR	101 (11.8)	21.05 $\pm$ 8.58
Smoking	Never Smoke	767 (89.4)	19.41 $\pm$ 8.09
	Previously smoked	13 (1.5)	24.08 $\pm$ 7.05
	Currently smokes	78 (9.1)	24.63 $\pm$ 6.91

* Ascertained by Independent samples' t-test

** Ascertained by One-way analysis of variance. Tukey's HSD test was applied where appropriate

*** PKR: Pakistani rupees

25(OH)D: 25-hydroxy vitamin D

ANOVA: Analysis of variance.

The dissimilarity in mean concentration values of 25(OH)D in different ethnic groups and groups with low standards of living ($P=0.083$, $P=0.267$) was not significant.

Comparative to males, females were found with low concentration of mean serum 25(OH)D ($P<0.001$). However, status of smoking and education effects the mean serum concentration of 25(OH)D. Mean serum concentrations of 25(OH)D was remarkably lower in non-smokers and people with formal education as compared to the smokers ($P<0.001$) and high education people ($P<0.001$) respectively. Smoking status of participants was examined further. It showed that cause of low mean to serum level of 25(OH)D was due to the fact that the number of women in this group was higher. 165 (47%) and 104 (21%) was the rate of distribution of insufficiency in males and females respectively. On the other hand, 115 (33%) and 386 (76%) was the extent of vitamin D deficiency in males and females respectively. The male and females who were finally vitamin D deficit / insufficient were 281 (80%) and 492 (97%) respectively. Final assessment was made for the widespread of vitamin D insufficiency and deficiency. It was found that insufficiency was 269 (31.4%) and deficiency was 501 (58.4%). The association between vitamin D deficiency and gender was observed through logistic regression model. After maintaining smoking and education status, this model illustrated that 6.69 was the value of deficiency in females comparative to males [OR (95%) confidence interval (CI) = 6.69 (4.63 – 9.67); ($P=0.001$)]. The Hosmer-Lemeshow Goodness of fit test was employed for the assessment of frequency of model by the addition of education & smoking status. No remarkable results were found. It indicates a good fit for modification of model ($\chi^2=3.519$; $df=6$; $P=0.733$).

DISCUSSION:

Comparative to male, the widespread of deficiency and insufficiency of vitamin D was mostly noticed in female population of Pakistan. This result is compatible with the result of studies carried out in the Pakistan previously [3-7]. According to the result of one such study, the percentage of deficiency / insufficiency in patients visiting Islamabad hospitals due to same disorder, was 25.5% [4]. The distinctive aspect of our study is that in this study, healthy people of Lahore were examined for deficiency and insufficiency of vitamin D. Another similar study was organized in Karachi with less number of individuals ($n=123$ Vs $n=858$). In this study the percentage of deficiency / insufficiency among physically fit females was 94.3%. In Islamabad, another study was conducted, in this study, total individuals were 737 [11]. For powerful and authentic results, the selection of individuals in our study was random, but in this study, the selection was not done randomly [10]. Likewise, an additional research study was conducted with large number of participants ($n=4,788$). All the participants who were assessed for the vitamin D deficiency / insufficiency on the recommendation of doctor. So, they were not healthy. On the other hand, participants of our study were not having any kind of disorder. Another study was conducted on Baharini mothers. As compared to educated females, the extent of deficiency of vitamin D was higher in less educated females [12]. In another study held in Karachi, the percentage of deficiency of vitamin D in uneducated females was higher. In this study, the pregnant females were 11, out of which 7 were illiterate [13].

Similar outcomes were observed in the research study conducted in the furnished community. Comparative to those individuals who were with less than 7 years of education, higher serum levels of vitamin D were found in people with higher education [14]. Socio-economic standard of population is also associated with sufficiency or insufficiency of vitamin D in addition to education.

As compared to men the value of OR (6.69) was higher in women which shows that females were much likely to have deficiency of vitamin D especially females having low living standard. Various factors contribute to low level of serum in females living in Lahore. Some factors are polluted air, insufficient exposure of skin to sunlight, houses with limited open space, multiparity and vitamin D deficit diet [15]. It is a duty of public health professionals to create awareness among people regarding healthy food with vitamin D and lifestyle in order to prevent vitamin D deficiency.

CONCLUSION:

The study concluded that in urban community, the shortage of vitamin D is more in females as compared to males which is a serious hazard to people health. Medical staff should resolve this issue by giving people attention.

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